

JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE FLOWING INPUT AND RELEASE

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ANNOTATION .

This JAVA programming in the article in the language flowing input and release functions about information given _ From this except information from the file reading functions and from the file to study circle program code cause passed

ANNOTATION.

This article provides information about streaming input and output functions in the JAVA programming language. In addition, the functions of reading data from a file and the program code for reading from a file are mentioned

Enter

How many abstract classes specialize in input and output in JAVA . They work differently with disk files, tape drives, and memory buffers account takes. Input Stream abstract class _

Input Stream is an abstract class that provides a model of input streams in JAVA. This

of the class everyone styles 10 Exception throws an exception when an error occurs. Below are the methods of the Input Stream class

briefly given : .read ()

input to give character which is the next path in the flow whole in appearance returns _

. read (byte b []) tries to read at most b.length bytes from the input stream into the array b. Actually returns the number of bytes read from the stream.

. read (byte b [], int off, int len) from off element max len bytes b

to the array

tries to read by placing it . Returns the actual number of bytes read .

. skip (long n) tries to transfer n bytes in the input stream. Passing sent bytes the amount returns _

. available () present at the time to study road has been bytes the amount returns _

. close () closes the input source. This is the next step in reading this stream actions 10 Exceptio

to take will come .

- . mark (int readlimit) is the current incoming stream that can be used until readlimit bytes have been read position sign puts _
- . reset () stream indicator before installed to the mark returns _
- . mark Supported () if given stream mark/reset operations true if it supports returns _

Output Stream abstract class _

Output Stream is an abstract class called Input Stream. It provides a model of JAVA's outgoing streams. All methods of this class have void type and throw 10 Exception on error

the sheep is gone . Below this class styles list listed :

- .write(int b) writes one byte to the output stream. Note that this method has a base type of int , which allows you to call write by passing an expression to cast its type to byte of execution need no .
- . write (byte b []) writes the entire specified byte array to the output stream.
- . write (byte b [], int off, int len) starting at element b (off). to the flow of the array part - len bytes writing takes _
- . flush () completes the output operation and clears any output buffers.
- . close () closes the output stream. This is the next step in writing to the stream action 10 Exception

provokes .

File flows .

File Input Stream. This class is used to input data from files. The example given below is one disc the file handler this of the class two object is made .

```
Input Stream f ( ) = new File Input Stream (" autoexe . bat ");
File f = new File("autoexe.bat");Input Stream f 1 = new FileInput Stream(f);
```

When an object of the File Input Stream class is created, it is opened for reading at one point. File Input Stream Overrides six methods of the Input Stream abstract class. Applying the mark and reset methods to an object of this class throws a 10 Exception . unread how much byte

the rest , and using the skip method you want to study didn't happen bytes skippable .

```
import java . io .*;
import java. wtil .* ;
class FileInput Stream S {
```



```
public static void main (string args [ ]) throws Exception}
```

```
int size;  
input Stream f1 = new FileInputStream ("/ wwwroot /default.htm")  
size = f1.available ( ); system . out. println ("Total Available Bytes :" + size);  
system. out. println ("First ¼ of the full : read ( )");  
for ( int i = 0; i < size / 4; i ++ ) {  
System . out. print ((char) f1 . read ( ));}System . out. println ("Total Still Available  
:" + f1. available ( ));  
System. out. println ("Reading the next 1/8 : read (b [ ])");  
byte b [ ] = new byte [ size / 8 ];  
if (f1. read (b) != b . length) {System . err . println ("Something bad happened");  
}String tmpstr = new String (b, 0, 0, b. length);  
System . out . println ( tmpstr );  
System . out . println ("Still Available : " + f1. available ( ));  
System . out . println ("Skipping another ¼ : skip ( )");  
f1 . skip (size / 4); System . out . println ("Still Available : " + f1.available ( ));  
System . out . println ("Reading 1/16 into the end of array");  
if (f1 . read (b, b . length - size / 16, size / 16) != size / 16) {System . err. println  
("Something bad happened");  
}System . out . println ("Still Available : " + f1 . available ( )); f1 . close ( );}}File
```

Output Stream. File Output Stream class same as File Input Stream two the same so constructor . But this class objects file does not exist strictly look make up can _ File Output Stream class when creating a new object release for the file opening it. In our next example, characters entered from the keyboard are System . in – one character per call from the stream

is calculated until the 12-byte buffer is not full. After that, three files will be created. To the first of them, file1.txt, characters are written from the buffer, but not all, some - zero, second and hock. To the second, file2.txt, to the clipboard fell everyone

entries are written. And finally half of the buffer in the middle to the third file is written , of the buffer the first and last quarters is not released .
import java. to *;

```
class File Output Stream S { public static byte getInput ( ) [ ] throws Exception {  
byte buffer [ ] = new byte [12]; for ( int i = 0; i < 12; i ++ ) {  
buffer [ i ] = (byte) System . in . read ( );}
```



```
return buffer;} public static void main (String args [ ]) throws Exception {  
byte buf [ ] = getInput ( );  
Output Stream f0 = new File Output Stream("file1.txt");Output Stream f1 = new  
File Output Stream("file2.txt");Output Stream f2 = new File Output  
Stream("file3.txt");for ( int i = 0; i < 10; i +=2) {  
f0.write ( buf [ i ]);}  
f0.close ( );f1. write ( buf );  
f1.close ( );  
f2.write ( buf , 12/4, 12/2);  
f2.close ( );}  
}
```

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